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“AFRICAN SWINE FEVER IN THE VISAYAS: SHIFTING FROM EMERGENCY RESPONSE TO SUSTAINABLE BIOSECURITY”

Introduction

When African Swine Fever (ASF) was first detected in the Philippines back in 2019. The reaction was fast and immediate. Hoping to contain the disease and stop it from becoming an outbreak. However, years have passed and still we are facing the problem head-on, especially in the Visayas, where government agencies are still struggling to contain it. What started as an emergency, now has become a long battle, revealing not only the weaknesses in the animal health system of our country but also the lapses in the farming communities. Even though policies and scientific tools have improved over time, the daily struggles of small farmers show a more complicated reality. In conversations with farmers and local stakeholders, it becomes evident that official measures often fail to align with on-the-ground realities. Tackling ASF now isn't just about quick responses, it requires a shift towards a sustainable biosecurity that truly reflects the daily struggles of those most affected.

Economic Impact: More Than Just Numbers

While losses due to ASF are reflected to be in Billions of pesos, the real loss that many failed to see lies in the local communities where farmers have to make the tough choices. With over 70% of pig farmers in the country belonging to smallholders (Hernandez et al., 2023), ASF's impact can truly be felt in many homes, not just in statistics. Fearing from forced culling and unjust compensation, many farmers in rural areas especially backyard raisers, often avoid protocols. It is a common knowledge how most handles suspect cases. Pigs showing early signs of illness are quickly slaughtered for pork or sold through informal channels. Many farmers while they are knowledgeable of the risks involved, the pressure of investment loss and profit, are left with little choice but to prioritize immediate needs over long-term protocols. As Fernandez-Colorado et al. (2024) points out, official responses often failed to see how financial pressure drives these decisions.

Policy Measures: A Framework Tested by Reality

Programs like INSPIRE (Integrated National Swine Production Initiatives for Recovery and Expansion) and zoning systems (Gomez, 2024) though it offered clear strategies, often fail to materialize. Farmers, afraid of losing their livelihood overnight, sometimes see reporting outbreaks as too risky. When you take the time to immerse with them, their recurring sentiment is skepticism which is rooted from past experiences where

support was either delayed, insufficient, and often unrealistic. This only shows that policies, no matter how well-designed, need to connect better with the realities farmers face daily.

Science and Biosecurity: Tools Without Trust?

There's no doubt that technologies developed to combat this disease, like the ASFV Nanogold Biosensor (OpenGov Asia, 2025), has improved detection. But as long as local pig producers openly hide cases out of fear, even the best tools won't help. If this continues, backyard farms will remain the most vulnerable (Lopez et al., 2024). Commercial and other large-scale farms are quick to adopt to proven protocols, but as long as local communities stay under the radar, all of this will be pointless. One farmer openly expressed that reporting suspected cases felt like "giving away" his livelihood, highlighting how fear often outweighs compliance. This only proves that to truly attain sustainable biosecurity, trust and understanding should go hand in hand with scientific advancement.

Community Engagement: Awareness vs. Action

Awareness campaigns have effectively delivered its intended goal. However, knowing what to do doesn't solve the financial problems of majority of the local farmers. In places like Aurora, families have had to adapt to lost income and changing work patterns (Santos et al., 2024). First-hand accounts revealed that even the most knowledgeable farmers are forced to undertake measures between adhering to biosecurity protocols and meeting their immediate economic needs. Without a clear and realistic financial support, farmers will always be left in a position where survival often dictates this action over compliance.

Conclusion

ASF in the Visayas is more than just an animal health crisis. It highlights the discrepancies between disease control, economic survival, and social behavior. Recognizing this, it becomes clear that sustainable long-term biosecurity must go beyond regulatory frameworks and engage with the lived experiences of farmers. Solutions that fail to overlook real challenges because of need for immediate implementation will likely fail to solve the very problem it is intended to solve. Therefore, in order to achieve sustainable ASF management scientific progress should include genuine understanding of the realities that is happening behind every farm gate.

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